

A Comparative Analysis of Different Algorithms for Optimizing Cutting Force Components in Turning Stainless Steel

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Abstract. Improved turning performance is critical for higher quality goods to be manufactured and costs to be reduced. The objective of this paper is to determine the optimal cutting parameters that minimize the net force in turning AISI 201 stainless steel using different mathematical optimization algorithms. Spindle speed, feed, depth of cut, and workpiece diameter were selected as process parameters. L_{16} Taguchi Design of Experiments were employed which includes four factors and four levels. In addition, regression models were developed to estimate cutting forces. Then several mathematical optimization algorithms were used to find the optimal parameters that minimize the net force. The algorithms employed in this paper were brute force algorithm, genetic algorithm, SHGO algorithm and basin-hopping algorithm. These algorithms are able to find optimal solutions of a set of equations with bounds and constraints. Both deterministic and non-deterministic techniques were used in these algorithms to achieve the optimized value. The optimal parameters in this investigation were cutting speed 245 rpm, feed 0.17 mm/rev, depth of cut 0.2 mm and workpiece diameter 19.1 mm.

Keywords: Turning, Machining parameter, Cutting force, Optimization, Genetic Algorithm.

1 Introduction

Turning is the process of using a cutting tool such as a lathe to manufacture parts of a particular size and shape out of materials such as metal. The forces created by the cutting tool impacts the cutting process and the quality of the final product greatly. The performance of the workpiece is primarily affected by the conditions of the turning

process. It is possible to approximate the characteristics of the workpiece using mathematical models by carefully controlling the process variables. Mathematical optimization algorithms can be utilized to find the best parameters of the empirical model for optimizing a particular response factor. Many studies have been published over the years that analyze the effects of various turning process parameters and the optimization of cutting force parameters.

Experimental research was carried out by Sahoo [1] for optimizing surface roughness. The author in that paper used response surface methodology and genetic algorithm for finding optimal values. Azizi et al. [2] discussed minimizing both cutting force and surface roughness using a desirability function. They used AISI 52100 steel with coated $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{TiC}$ mixed ceramic cutting tools for their experiment. Ponugoti et al. [3] used hybrid grey relational analysis and principal component analysis to determine the optimal parameters for hard turning AISI 52100 grade steel. Ahilan et al. [4] used a technique based on grey systems theory for optimizing multiple response factors. Using grey based Taguchi method, they were able to optimize surface roughness and power usage. Singh et al. [5] modeled the output responses using a regression model and used a desirability function to optimize cutting parameters. The authors used AISI 4340 grade steel with Cr_2O_3 doped ceramic insert for their conducting their experiment. Singaravel et al. [6] experimented with tuning turning parameters for EN25 steel with coated carbide tools. They used the entropy measurement method and optimized response factors such as surface roughness and material removal rate using Multi-Objective Optimization by Ratio Analysis (MOORA). Tamizharasan et al. [7] found optimal turning conditions using design of experiments and by analyzing audible acoustic signals. They used simulated annealing algorithm and regression analysis for finding the optimal values. Sahali et al. [8] used P-NSGA-II, a type of genetic algorithm, to solve multi-objective optimization problems for turning parameters. In the dry turning of Inconel of 718 employing coated inserts, Ramanujan et al. [9] analyzed optimization modeling and trimming parameters. The experiment was based on Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array, turning tests were performed at different stages of cutting parameters to test the output factor, such as roughness of the cutting force surface and wear of the instruments. A mathematical analysis of ANOVA findings found that feed rate and cuts depth have the highest response weight.

Although a large amount of work has been focused on optimizing cutting conditions for cutting force components and surface roughness using different grades of steel, there are no works that discuss optimizing cutting parameters for the turning of AISI 201 grade stainless steel utilizing empirical models and mathematical optimization algorithms. In the current study, experiments were conducted using AISI 201 steel. The cutting forces were estimated with a regression model and optimal cutting parameters were found using mathematical optimization routines.

2 Experimental Setup

2.1 Workpiece and cutting tool material

AISI 201 stainless steel was used as a workpiece in the experiment which includes carbon (Max 0.15%), silicon (max 0.75%), manganese (5.5-7.5%), phosphorus (max 0.06%), sulfur (max 0.03%), nickel (3.5-5.5%), chromium (16-18%) and nitrogen (max 0.25%) [10]. For the procedure, Cemented carbide cutting tool insert was used. Cemented carbide is a durable material that is commonly used in cutting machining equipment, as well as many manufacturing applications.

2.2 Experiment Design

In order to create relations between the machining parameters and process parameters, the Taguchi method was used. Four main processing parameters were defined including spindle speed (N), feed (f), depth of cut (ap) and workpiece diameter (D) in this experiment. The four levels for each machining parameter are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Selection of cutting parameters

Cutting parameters	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
Spindle speed (rpm)	245	490	650	800
Feed (mm/rev)	0.12	0.14	0.16	0.18
Depth of cut (mm)	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50
Workpiece diameter (mm)	19.10	24.00	31.75	40.00

The current study describes the relationship between the input called cutting speed (N), feed (f), cutting depth (ap) and workpiece diameter (D) and the output factor R as

$$R = \varnothing (N, f, ap, D) \quad (1)$$

Where \varnothing is the response function. The tangential (F_t), axial (F_a) and radial (F_r) forces are the selected response factors in the current study. The machining parameters (N, f, ap, D) and the values of output variables F_t , F_a , F_r for all experimental runs are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Design of Experiments

Run N ^o	Machining parameters				Responses		
	N (rpm)	F (mm/rev)	A_p (mm)	D (mm)	F_t (KN)	F_a (KN)	F_r (KN)
1	245	0.16	0.2	19.10	0.06	0.02	0.07
2	245	0.12	0.3	24.00	0.16	0.10	0.15
3	245	0.14	0.4	31.75	0.09	0.04	0.12
4	245	0.18	0.5	40.00	0.32	0.15	0.29
5	490	0.16	0.3	31.75	0.12	0.05	0.15
6	490	0.12	0.2	40.00	0.10	0.06	0.16
7	490	0.14	0.5	19.10	0.08	0.04	0.09
8	490	0.18	0.4	24.00	0.19	0.09	0.19
9	650	0.16	0.4	40.00	0.19	0.09	0.12
10	650	0.12	0.5	31.75	0.06	0.04	0.09
11	650	0.14	0.2	24.00	0.05	0.04	0.08
12	650	0.18	0.3	19.10	0.04	0.02	0.07
13	800	0.16	0.5	24.00	0.02	0.12	0.17
14	800	0.12	0.4	19.10	0.04	0.03	0.06
15	800	0.14	0.3	40.00	0.12	0.07	0.19
16	800	0.18	0.2	31.75	0.03	0.01	0.07

Fig. 1(a) and Fig. 1(b) show the work piece and cutting tool used for the experimentation. Dynamometer was used to measure the cutting force which is shown in Fig. 1(c). To achieve higher resolution, an L₁₆ OA was selected for experimentation. The analyses were conducted on the basis of L₁₆ OA.

(a) Work Piece (b) Cutting Tool (c) Dynamometer

Fig. 1. Work piece, cutting tool and device used in the investigation

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Regression Analysis

The cutting forces can be approximated using various mathematical models. In this study, regression models were chosen for their simplicity and the ability to generalize well to unseen data. Three regression models were developed from the experimental data in Table 3.

The regression models for the tangential force(F_t), the axial force(F_a) and the radial force(F_r) are given in equation (1), (2) and (3)-

$$F_t = 1.317 - 0.000547 N - 7.24 f - 3.280 ap - 0.00773 D + 0.00180 N \times f + 0.000189 N \times ap + 0.000007 N \times D + 20.63 f \times ap + 0.0013 f \times D + 0.0168 ap \times D \quad (1)$$

$$F_a = 0.944 - 0.00047 N - 5.21 f - 2.061 ap - 0.00461 D + 0.00226 N \times f + 0.000111 N \times ap + 0.000005 N \times D + 12.48 f \times ap + 0.0111 f \times D + 0.01202 ap \times D \quad (2)$$

$$F_r = 0.514 - 0.000230 N - 2.98 f - 1.55 ap + 0.00574 D + 0.00002 N \times f - 0.000096 N \times ap + 0.000009 N \times D + 13.20 f \times ap - 0.0433 f \times D - 0.0066 ap \times D \quad (3)$$

Their coefficients of determination (R^2) are 92.31%, 90.95% and 86.88% for equations (1), (2) and (3). The cutting force components are estimated using the turning parameters as input.

3.2 Parameter Optimization

In the current study, the goal is to minimize the cutting force components to improve machining performance. To achieve this, an objective function must be defined to decrease all three force components. In this case, the objective function is the net cutting force. As the three forces are perpendicular to each other, the net force can be calculated using the principles of mechanics [11].

$$F_{net} = \sqrt{F_t^2 + F_a^2 + F_r^2}$$

The three component forces are approximated by three regression models. Since the optimization will be based on these regression models built on experimental data, the variables were bounded by the lowest and highest values of the experimental values. Variables were bounded because it could not be guaranteed that the empirical models will give accurate results for input parameters that are outside the range of values these models were fitted on.

$$N \in [245, 900], f \in [0.12, 0.2], ap \in [0.2, 0.5], D \in [18, 50]$$

Moreover, there was also a minimum bound on the three component forces F_t , F_a and F_r . This was done because of the lowest force recorded experimentally was 0.01

$$F_t > 0.01, F_a > 0.01, F_r > 0.01$$

With these constraints, four algorithms were employed to optimize the cutting force parameters. Brute-force algorithm, SHGO (simplicial homology global optimization), genetic algorithm and Basin-hopping.

Brute-force Algorithm. In the brute-force algorithm, all possible candidates for the solution are evaluated and the best one is chosen [12]. However, it is not feasible to evaluate all possible parameters in a reasonable amount of time. So only the parameters in Table 1 were considered part of the solution space. Considering all possible combinations of the parameters in Table 1, there are 256 unique sets of parameter combinations available. After evaluating all these sets, the optimal set was chosen given the constraints. The results obtained by the brute-force algorithm is shown in Table 4.

SHGO. Simplicial homology algorithm is a general-purpose global optimization algorithm [13]. It is a powerful algorithm capable of finding global minima or maxima of a function. It works even with black-box functions i.e. it does not require knowing the structure of the function it optimizes. So it is suited for finding optimal parameters of complex models developed using empirical data. An implementation of the algorithm can be found in the scipy library [14] in the python programming language. The default configurations were used to find the optimal parameters. The results are shown in Table 4.

Genetic Algorithm. The genetic algorithm is based on the principles of natural selection from the theory of evolution. A set of factors generate candidate solutions. Based on a fitness metric, it evaluates the candidate solutions. Then the selected factors recombine and reproduce to create new sets of candidate solutions. Over many generations, the algorithm slowly converges to the optimal solution. This algorithm can be utilized to solve many different types of problems. It can also be used to find the global minima of a function with constraints. An implementation of the algorithm can be found in the genetic algorithm library [15] in the python programming language. The number of generations the algorithm would run was set at 3000. The other configurations were left at their default values. The results are shown in Table 4.

Basin-hopping. Basin-hopping is a stochastic global optimization algorithm [16]. It runs perturbations on the acquired solutions based on Monte-Carlo methods in a single iteration and uses a second optimization algorithm for finding the local minima again. It is a versatile algorithm capable of handling functions with many local minima. An implementation of the algorithm can be found in the scipy library in the python programming language.

The number of iterations for the algorithm was set at 100. The second optimization algorithm was set to trust-constr in scipy, as this algorithm is capable of finding minima with bounds and constraints. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Optimized parameters obtained by the different algorithms

Algorithm	N (rpm)	F (mm/rev)	a_p (mm)	D (mm)	F_t (KN)	F_a (KN)	F_r (KN)	F_{net} (KN)
Brute Force	245.0	0.18	0.2	19.1	0.008865	0.05266	0.0603	0.080546
SHGO	900.0	0.12	0.35	18.0	0.0112	0.07538	0.04723	0.08966
Genetic Algorithm	280.3	0.187	0.2212	18.14	0.01005	0.05073	0.06672	0.08442
Basin hopping	245.0	0.180	0.2	18.0	0.01	0.05041	0.06094	0.07972

4 Result Analysis

From the data, it can be seen that the best parameters were determined by basin-hopping algorithm. And the optimal parameters are cutting speed 245 rpm, feed 0.18 mm/rev, depth of cut 0.2 mm and workpiece diameter 18 mm. Basin-hopping algorithm provides the best overall result across all three cutting force components, as seen in Figure 2.

Fig.2. Comparison of different algorithms for minimizing all forces

Brute force algorithm also performs sufficiently after basin-hopping. However, it is a very computationally expensive algorithm. This method may not be suitable in other applications.

SHGO also produces acceptable results. This algorithm is the fastest of the four. SHGO is rather well suited for optimizing functions with low dimensionality, as it is in this study. The optimized net force from SHGO is about 0.01 KN lower than the lowest net force estimated from all other algorithms.

Genetic algorithm performs adequately. It is worth mentioning that while genetic algorithm is powerful, it takes many generations for it to produce optimal results. In general, it performs slower than basin-hopping and SHGO but it doesn't give better results than these two algorithms.

It is worth mentioning that there is a significant difference from the lowest two performing algorithms to the highest two performing algorithms. This fact is better highlighted in Figure 3, where only the optimal net force determined by the algorithms are shown.

Fig.3. Comparison of different algorithms for minimizing net force

5 Conclusions

In this study, experiments were conducted on turning AISI 201 grade steel with a cemented carbide cutting tool. The experiment design was employed based on the principles of the Taguchi method. Then regression models were developed based on experimental data. Then using the empirical models, optimal cutting parameters were determined. Several conclusions can be drawn from the experiment. Firstly, in the turning of AISI 201 stainless steel, cutting speed 245 rpm, feed 0.17 mm/rev, depth of cut 0.2 mm and workpiece diameter 19.1 mm are appropriate for minimizing the net cutting force. Secondly, Basin-hopping algorithm is the best overall performing algorithm for optimization. It can also be observed that regression models for approximating workpiece response factors can be developed and be utilized for further analysis. More sophisticated models can be developed using artificial neural networks and decision trees. They can also be used with mathematical optimization algorithms to determine ideal conditions for the turning process. The performance of these models can be investigated in a future study.

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